

Occupational Therapy As A Strategic Use Of Strength For Foster Learning Of Children Due To Mental Health Problems In Early Years At Karachi, Pakistan

Rabia Abdul Karim, Anila Fatima Shakil, Shazia Inayat Ali, Nadia Parveen Thalho

Article Info	Abstract
<p data-bbox="199 504 368 530">Article History</p> <p data-bbox="199 562 352 622">Received: May 29, 2021</p> <p data-bbox="199 658 392 719">Accepted: October 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p data-bbox="199 750 328 777">Keywords :</p> <p data-bbox="199 781 443 929">Occupational therapy, Strategic, Foster learning, Mentally Disabled, Communication skills.</p> <p data-bbox="199 965 268 992">DOI:</p> <p data-bbox="199 996 480 1023">10.5281/zenodo.5639900</p>	<p data-bbox="560 504 1401 1104"><i>This research study emphasized on the importance of therapies especially Occupational therapy (OT) for the disabled children vis-à-vis the complexity of learning regarding it as a tool for adjustment in the schools. In the past, education for mentally disabled children was controversial topic, as it was a most challenging task for concern stakeholders to deal with such children in a normal school environment. Therefore, many efforts were made to provide an educational environment for these children to deal with day-to-day activities and learning challenges in collaboration with some therapies in which Occupational Therapy (OT) is playing a vital role by providing facilities and enable them to function to the best of their abilities by reducing an environment barrier that limits a child participation in learning. The methodology of this research study was based on qualitative cum quantitative method and the data was collected from the 170 trainers of 02 universities and 15 parents from 03 schools of disabled children regarding to Occupational therapy (OT) in Karachi. The questionnaire and interview were used as the research instrument and in the light of results; recommendations were also presented for the promotion of Occupational therapy (OT) for such children to cope up with their needs and facilitate teachers by providing them support to enhance their teaching skills through the use of Occupational Therapy for better learning-teaching process.</i></p>

Introduction

Education is a manifestation of divine protection already existing in man. It is the developmental process of the soul beauty and protection of body and soul of child (Hare, R.M 1989). It is an essential part of society that develops individual as per demand of society. As John Dewey said "Education is not preparation for life, education is life its-self." (Dewey John 1961). Therefore, it has been declared as a compulsory unit to get education for all peoples including normal as well as disabled children, so they can able to get suitable social status. Therefore, it was realized that beginning must be made somewhere in actual life of an individual to prepare an individual for his living. Thus the first major step to the development of individual was taken with the establishment of formal Institutions. But however, only normal people were facilitated by these institutions and there was no place for mentally disable peoples to get education in formal manner as same as normal people. Though education is has been declared as a compulsory unit for all peoples, normal as well as important and necessary for disabled people.

In the Previous place of society, the birth of a disable child was seen as a punishment or as a work of evil. These people were understood as the curse of God or the sin of parents. But however, with the passage of time and the advancement in education, people get awareness to the fact that Disable children have same rights and place in the society as normal one.

According to the act of an individual with Disability Education (IDEA) the disable child, who having the following mental and physical impairments like hearing and health, having autism, traumatic injuries and learning disabilities (IDEA, 1997).

Disability has been defined as "standard impairment of some organ or brain which results in impairments of certain functions". A person can be regarded as a mental disabled if they are judged to a failure to cope with the intellectual demands of their environment (Whitaker, 2008). The mental and physical disabilities are impacted on child daily performance. Therefore, in primitive society, the education of disabled children was most controversial topic amongst the educators as it was a most challenging task for teachers to deal with a disabled child in normal school environment. Thus, by the passage of time and advancement in education and learning approaches various institutions are established where latest trends, activities and therapies are used for disabled children to assist them to cope with their needs and play active role in the society. Among them Occupational Therapy is also providing required results regarding disabled children. Occupational Therapy (OT) designed to improve positive changes in a child's personality, behavior or adjustment. It focused on the primary

level of disabled education and provides a measure for foster learning of mentally retarded children through occupational therapy.

Occupational Therapy provides the great help to the people without discrimination of age and other deficits regain and develop skills that help functioning healthy life. It is beneficial in early childhood life and help to improve healthy life.

The purpose of occupational therapy is to develop people ability to his/her highest possible level, to enhance his quality of life and sense of wellbeing, to increase individual's satisfaction in daily living and to improve access to opportunities for participation in life situations. Hence, the core of occupational therapy is to enable an individual to interact a satisfying range of occupation that will support his daily life activities and sense of achievement within a society.

Aims of study:

- To investigate the practices of an occupational therapy with profound mental disabilities to engage in their occupation.
- To highlight the primary goal of occupational therapy which enable a child to participate in the activities of daily life?
- To identify the signs and symptoms which indicates the needs of occupational therapy for a child?
- To examine the instructional material & its equipment used by occupational therapist for the betterment adjustment of disabled child
- To examine the environmental barriers that limits a child participation in learning by means of OT.
- To encourage and promote occupational therapy providing awareness among parents of disabled child.

Review of related literature:

In every domain of life, the mental health plays a vital role to make life good and healthy. Its help to develop a good citizen, active member of the society, family institute, organization, country. It contributes to choose the better life and help to take a good decision in the life for individual own self and for the others (world health organization 2005).

- 450 million people experience mental health or neurobiological disorders around the world. These disorders constitute 5-10 leading causes of disability around the world.
- Mental disorder can be diagnosed and treated cost-effectively.
- In many parts of the world mental health is still not acknowledged a Important and remains a low health priority. Access to effective treatment is limited.
- More than 27 % of adult around the world are estimated to experience at least one form of mental ill health during any one year.

Occupation and Health:

Ordinary occupation becomes a part of the context of daily living. Such are habitual and some are taking for granted (Wood, 2002). Occupation classified according to the culture and contains activities. The purpose of occupation is to to enabling the people to face the environmental challenges(Yexra.EJ,1993).

*Self-care

*Playleisure.

*Productivity work.

There are artificial differentiations, since an occupation n move from one category to another or belong in more than one category at the same time.

The function of occupation: People have a basic need to engage in activity that has meaning and value for them. Reilly (1969) claimed that man has a vital need for occupation and that his central nervous system demands the rich and varied stimuli that solving life problems provide him. Hence the occupation and the activity which they are enacted, can serve various function in daily life.

* Occupations provide for the essential needs of the organism. (Wilcock,1998)

*People develop and maintain function through being active. (Baum, 1973)

*Physical, cognitive and emotional development are influenced by the physical, and mental activity of the growing child. (Ostoval R,2009)

*Occupation contributes to an individual's personal sense of identity. (Hesselcuss, 2002)

*Occupation is a tool for learning exploring, and developing competence. (Passmore,2003)

*The health & wellbeing of an individual is influenced by what he does. (Hassellkuss,2002)

*Occupation form an important part of each person's social identity &social status. (Washon, 2004)

Occupational therapist claims there is a link between occupation and health (Wilcock 1998) argues that humans are occupational being with a central system that has the capacity to analyses, organize, understand, produce, judge, plan, activate, formulate & execute complex occupation. The three factorswhich effects the health of

individuals are occupational imbalance, deprivation and alienation that are cause a breakdown of individual's occupation.

Historical context of occupational therapy: At the beginning of 20th century, the most important influence on psychiatry were the theories of Sigmund Freud (1856-1973) & Alfred Adler (1870-1937) who developed psycho analysis and psychotherapy.

The first training started in UK and in first two decade context and circumstances needed for function of occupational therapy.

Another major influence on psychiatry was Adolt Meryer (1866-1950) who viewed mental illness as the outcome of a person's maladaptive interaction with the environment. Influenced by Meyer, Professor Sir David Henderson (1884-1965) worked as an influential figure in the development of occupational therapy throughout first half of 20th century.

Identification of Occupational therapy:

The condition in which occupational therapy is needed are categorize into groups i.e.

*Sensory integration disorders

* Execution functioning issues

*Visual processing issues

*Speech & language issues

*Developmental co-ordination issues

To cope with such issues & have better adjustment within environment occupational therapy is essential.

Hypothesis:

There will be significant difference on student's communication skills by the application of OT

There will be significant difference on healthy life style of students having OT

There will be significant difference by OT on student's learning.

There will be significant difference on student's social development by the application of OT

There will be significant difference by OT on the sensory training of student.

There will be significance difference by the application of OT on the vocational training of students.

Methodology:

The methodology of this research study was based on qualitative cum quantitative methods and the population of this study was 2 universities and 3 schoolsof disabled children regarding occupational therapy. Within the population, 170 trainers and 15 parents were selected for the data collection. The questionnaire and interview methods were used as the research instruments. After the collection of data statistical analysis was done by the application of SPSS.

Results from questionnaire:

The collected data from the trainers related to the study through questionnaire was analyzed by the application of One sample t-test and Cronbach's Alpha.

Hypothesis Analysis

Table 1

H1 There will be significant difference on healthy life style of students having OT

	N	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean	SD
HLS 5	170	-99.156	.000	1.76	.425
HLS 6	170	-68.846	.000	1.55	.653
HLS 7	170	-77.116	.000	1.67	.563
HLS 8	170	-94.377	.000	1.71	.454

Cronbach's Alpha .843

It is significant at 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Table 2

H2 There will be significant difference by OT on student's learning

	N	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean	SD
SL 9	170	-51.571	.000	1.73	.827
SL 10	170	-90.236	.000	1.54	.500
SL 11	170	-59.659	.000	1.68	.725
SL 12	170	-55.591	.000	1.74	.766

Cronbach's Alpha.935

It is significant at 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Table 3

H3 There will be significant difference on student's social development by the application of OT

	N	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean	SD
SD 13	170	-69.992	.000	1.69	.616
SD 14	170	-71.608	.000	1.59	.048
SD 15	170	-69.250	.000	1.52	.050
SD 16	170	-96.200	.000	1.74	.034

Cronbach's Alpha.798

It is significant at 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Table 4

H 4 There will be significant difference by OT on the sensory training of student.

	N	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean	SD
ST 17	170	-67.717	.000	1.68	.640
ST 18	170	-64.059	.000	1.61	.690
ST 19	170	-100.588	.000	1.78	.418

Cronbach's Alpha.729

It is significant at 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Table 5

H 5 There will be significance difference by the application of OT on the vocational training of students.

	N	t	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean	SD
VT 20	170	-57.137	.000	1.67	.058
VT 21	170	-61.179	.000	1.71	.054
VT 22	170	-79.481	.000	1.75	.041
VT23	170	-94.793	.000	1.72	.034

Cronbach's Alpha.832

It is significant at 0.01 level (2 tailed)

Results from interview:

Beside questionnaire, the researcher conducted interviews from the parents of concern children to highlight the need of occupational therapy for better learning-teaching process. The conclusion of parents from interview is as follow:

- 50% parents said that at the time of birth there was no such disability among their child and 50% said their child was disabled by birth.
- 80% parents reported that their child had a concentration issues and can easily distracted by noise, bright light, hunger etc.
- 78% parents said that their child have difficulty while mastering simple motor activities and the remaining parents identified that their child is over sensitive to things related to their environment due to which they had trouble receiving & responding to information that comes through senses.
- 40% parents said that their child had a difficulty in understanding what other say even they are unable to answer simple questions as well as face challenges in pronouncing specific sounds and words.
- 100% parents claimed that they see good change in their child with the support of this therapy as their child will become independent enough & function to the best of their activity.

From the above responses of parents, it has been noticed that occupational therapy has

Discussion:

Occupational therapy enables an individual to engage in effective activities in the daily life.

This therapy helps to improve the daily life and develop the child's social and interpersonal skills and enable them to become an effective member of society.

This supports and promotes learning and gives children an understanding of appropriate behavior. Hence the occupational therapist is concerned with the clear picture of child's development, and strives to ensure that all aspects are being addressed so you child can achieve his/her maximum potential. On the other hand, occupational therapy provides families to identify and support their child's holistic development through using a child's interest. Hence OT understand the impact of the environment on child and can help parents and teachers to develop strategies that can help a child to cope better in the environment that they find challenging. Thus occupational therapy plays a unique role in modifying the environment in order to facilitate productive and meaningful use of physical and intellectual capacities of concern children and enable them to contribute their role in the society.

Recommendations:

- OT should their practice and activities in general schools as well.
- OT should be made affordable for children and families to access its services without any hurdles.
- OT must ensure on equal access and participation in education of all child.
- Therapist should aware parents about the scope and functions of OT & its implementation in their region.
- There must be at least one occupational therapist in every school for helping children with learning difficulties.
- Occupational therapy sessions must be conducted for parents and teachers to make them aware of useful strategies.
- Universities should introduce occupational therapy programs and courses for students within affordable fees structure.
- More specialized equipment is needed to be used in schools under the guidance of occupational therapist.
- Parents should also cooperate with occupational therapist and do their best for the well-being of their child.
- State should support this kind of therapy in every region because these children are also the future of our nation.

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Author Information

Dr. Rabia Abdul Karim

Associate Professor, Department of Education,
Jinnah University for Women, Karachi

Dr. Anila Fatima Shakil

Associate Professor, Department of Education,
Jinnah University for Women, Karachi

Ms Shazia Inayat Ali

Lecturer, Department of Education, Jinnah
University for Women, Karachi

Nadia Parveen Thalho

Instructor/Lecturer Government Elementary College
of Women Hyderabad Sindh Pakistan
